

BIOPOLE Newsletter

Autumn 2023

compiled by Ruta Hamilton (BAS)

Welcome to our seasonal newsletter!

As I write this introduction, I know that some BIOPOLE scientists will be in the midst of packing their bags ready for the journey to the Southern Ocean to join the RRS Sir David Attenborough on its first ever dedicated science mission. The scientific cruise we call BIOPOLE I (cruise name SD033), will take place between Dec 5th and 16th as part of a wider expedition involving logistical runs to the BAS bases at the Antarctic Peninsula, South Orkneys and South Georgia. The BIOPOLE team will be led by Andrew Meijers with a mission to make physical, biogeochemical and biological measurements at the ice-edge in the Weddell Sea. Their measurements will further our understanding of how polar oceanic waters are conditioned to facilitate the huge pulse of productivity we observe in these regions during spring. In addition to ship-based sampling, the mission will deploy a number of autonomous underwater vehicles (underwater gliders) which will keep measuring this region for many months after the ship has left. Good luck to Andrew and his team.

Also in this newsletter, you can find out more on the successful UKCEH-led Arctic sampling expedition to Ny Ålesund carried out this summer. Alanna Grant has written a wonderful account of their time in Svalbard, of the spectacle of nature they observed and the scientific sampling they got stuck into.

The past months have also been productive ones for BIOPOLE outreach, with a ministerial briefing on our project, a panel discussion at the UK Arctic conference on our approach to reducing our carbon footprint, and a major input into the multinational programme SOOS collating and harmonising polar ocean observations and data.

Geraint Tarling (Principal Investigator)

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI)

The 18th of November 2023 marks both the international days of LGBTQIA+ STEM and Polar Pride. These special days coincide with the start of the first BIOPOLE cruise in the Southern Ocean. To celebrate the occasion and lend support to LGBTQIA+ people living, working or undertaking research in the polar regions, the 12 scientific members of the cruise (including BIOPOLE members [Andrew Meijers](#), [Alexander Brearley](#), [Gabriele Stowasser](#), [Nadine Johnston](#), [Laura Taylor](#), and [Petra ten Hoopen](#)) will be donning pride colours and flying the Pride Flag on the Sir David Attenborough before she sets sail for the Weddell Sea, capturing the moment to share widely through social media channels. To amplify the message, [Huw Griffiths](#), will be attending an event in the UK Houses of Parliament in London on the 20th of November (hosted by the All Party Parliamentary Group for the Polar Regions) in support of Polar Pride. Keep your eye out on X [@BIOPOLE_NERC](#) and read more about the importance of Polar Pride in the [Polar Regions Newsletter](#)!

Written by [Nadine Johnston](#), [Huw Griffiths](#), and [Laura Taylor](#)

BIOPOLE Paper of the Season

The paper examined the transfer of carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus and silica through the estuaries of four peat-dominated catchments in the Falkland Islands. In contrast to the estuaries of Europe and North America where most estuarine research takes place, we found that very little nitrogen or phosphorus was coming from the land. Instead, these key nutrients were entering the estuaries from the ocean, and appeared to drive estuarine diatom production as they mixed with silica from the rivers. This marine-driven estuarine productivity is considered relatively unusual, due to nutrient pollution of rivers by agriculture and urbanisation, but was probably far more widespread in the past. The Falkland estuaries may therefore offer an analogue for how other estuaries behaved in the past, and a better understanding of the processes that regulate nutrient cycling in the absence of human impacts. From a BIOPOLE perspective, the reason that the seas around the Falklands are so productive (and also a globally important fishery) is that ocean water enriched with nutrients from the Antarctic ice sheet are transported north from the Southern Ocean by the Falkland Current, which flows up the east coast of South America. The Falkland estuaries and its rich offshore waters can therefore be considered 'receptor' ecosystems for the polar nutrient generation processes being studied by BIOPOLE.

[Read the paper](#)

Marine nutrient subsidies promote biogeochemical hotspots in undisturbed, highly humic estuaries

Chris D. Evans ^{1,2*} Stacey L. Felgate,^{3,4,5} Steffi Carter,^{1,6} Mark Stinchcombe,⁴ Edward Mawji,⁴ Andrew P. Rees,⁷ Inma Lebron,¹ Richard Sanders,^{3,8} Paul Brickle,^{6,9} Daniel J. Mayor^{4,10}

¹UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, Bangor, UK

²Swedish Agricultural University, Uppsala, Sweden

³Ocean and Earth Science, University of Southampton, Southampton, UK

⁴Ocean Biogeosciences, National Oceanography Centre (NOC), Southampton, UK

⁵Department of Chemistry–BMC, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden

⁶South Atlantic Environmental Research Institute (SAERI), Stanley, Falkland Islands

⁷Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML), Plymouth, UK

⁸Norwegian Research Centre (NORCE), Bergen, Norway

⁹School of Biological Sciences (Zoology), University of Aberdeen, Aberdeen, Scotland, UK

¹⁰Biosciences, University of Exeter, Exeter, UK

Abstract

The land-ocean dissolved organic carbon (DOC) flux represents a significant term within the global carbon budget, with peatland-dominated regions representing the most intense sources of terrestrial DOC export. As the interface between freshwater and marine systems, estuaries have the potential to act as a filter of the land-ocean carbon flux, removing terrestrially derived DOC, which is present at low concentrations in the oceans, via a combination of physicochemical and biological processes. However, the fate of peat-derived DOC within estuaries remains poorly quantified, partly due to the complicating influences of heterogeneous soils, land-use, point sources, and upstream modification of organic matter. To minimize these modifying factors, we studied DOC and inorganic nutrients in four small, peat-dominated, minimally disturbed, and oligotrophic Falkland Island estuaries. Contrary to expectations, we found limited evidence of physicochemical estuarine DOC removal, and instead observed apparent “hot zones” of biogeochemical activity, where terrestrially-derived silicate mixed with inorganic nitrogen and phosphorus entering the estuaries from the nutrient-rich marine ecosystem. In two estuaries, this coincided with apparent in situ DOC production. We suggest that the observed phenomena of marine nutrient subsidy of estuarine productivity, and flexible utilization of multiple nutrients within the oligotrophic system, may once have been widespread in temperate estuaries. However, this function has been lost in many ecosystems due to catchment eutrophication by agricultural and urban development. We conclude that the estuaries of the Falkland Islands provide a valuable pre-disturbance analogue for natural biogeochemical functioning in temperate estuaries receiving high organic matter inputs.

Evans, C.D., Felgate, S.L., Carter, S., Stinchcombe, M.C., Mawji, E., Rees, A.P., Lebron, I., Sanders, R.R., Brickle, P., & Mayor, D.J. (2023). Marine nutrient subsidies promote biogeochemical hotspots in undisturbed, highly humic estuaries. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 68.

UKCEH Dips its Toes into (Arctic) Waters

It's been a month since the team's return to the UK from Ny Ålesund, Svalbard, and after a much needed two week holiday, I finally feel ready to put the proverbial pen to paper to put our epic BIOPOLE adventure into words. After re-reading my daily journal that I kept during the trip, I have realised that my ramblings completely failed to capture the utter privilege it was to spend time with these fantastic people and call this incredible place home for a month. So in this blog I will endeavour to expand on my scribbles and paint a picture for the reader that may just give them a small window into our month of thrilling polar science. It's a tale of an arctic escapade involving impossibly good weather, a heroic label printer, the Poet Laureate, a squeaky winch, and the most fetching orange boat suits.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Nathan laughing at Chris who has fallen over. Just kidding. The team taking samples and measurements from a river (not pictured).

Photo: Iain Rudkin

Written by [Alanna Grant](#). Contributors – Alex O'Brien and [Bryan Spears](#)

BIOPOLE in Net Zero Carbon Science Panel Discussion

During the UK Arctic Science Conference hosted by BAS (11-13 September), [Geraint Tarling](#) participated as panellist to a NZC session chaired by [Clara Manno](#). The session discussed opportunities across science disciplines to reduce carbon, with a particular focus on what the long-term challenges are to tackling net-zero in the Arctic.

There was a clear consensus on the need to develop high tech skills to prepare the next generation of scientists for an NZC future. It was also highlighted that the scientific community must embrace a cultural shift which includes better international collaboration. In this context, the BIOPOLE planning strategy was presented as a role model on how to reduce the carbon footprint in the Arctic by collaborating with those international colleagues already operating in the region. This obviated the need to deploy our own polar vessel, the Sir David Attenborough, to carry out the required sampling and measurements.

from September 11th to 13th

UK Arctic Science Conference

hosted at the British Antarctic Survey

Written by [Clara Manno](#)

BIOPOLE Meets Science Minister at BAS

On 31st October, the Minister of State for Science, Research and Innovation, [George Freeman](#) (MP), visited the [British Antarctic Survey](#) to update his knowledge on some of the latest science being carried out in the **Polar Regions**.

[Geraint Tarling](#) provided an overview of BIOPOLE to the minister, and engaged him in the importance of polar ecosystems to climate and ocean productivity. The minister was particularly interested in the use of AI in helping us predict variability in the biological carbon pump, with an eye on the upcoming International AI security conference at Bletchley Park the following day. Minister Freeman considers the UK to be a 'Polar Science Superpower' and on commenting on his visit, he noted how our scientists are – “committed to global science for global good in deep international collaborations with allied polar research nations”.

[Geraint Tarling](#) providing an overview of BIOPOLE to the Minister of State for Science, Research and Innovation, [George Freeman](#) (MP), at the [British Antarctic Survey](#) on the 31st of October 2023. Credit: Ruta Hamilton

Written by [Geraint Tarling](#)

Encouraging the Next Generation of Polar Biologists at Big Biology Day

On a sunny Saturday in October, BIOPOLE team member [Jen Freer](#) took part in the [Big Biology Day](#) at Hills Rd Sixth Form College in Cambridge. Along with others from the [British Antarctic Survey](#), this exciting event provided a wonderful chance to engage with people of all ages, expertise, interests and backgrounds, as well as inspire young people to pursue careers in polar science and exploration.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

BIOPOLE team member [Jen Freer](#) takes part in the Big Biology Day at Hills Rd Sixth Form College in Cambridge representing BIOPOLE

Written by [Jen Freer](#)

BIOPOLE at Bluedot 2023

A team of around 20 plucky [BAS](#) scientists including BIOPOLE members showcased our research, equipment, and facilities at [Bluedot](#), a family-oriented, science themed music festival held at [Jodrell Bank](#) telescope array in **Manchester**.

There was lots of public interest in BIOPOLE, from children, parents, students, half-cut scallywags, and a few other marine scientists – everyone really. As BIOPOLE is such a wide-ranging project we could discuss many aspects of ocean science so, even though immediately grabbing people’s attention to a heavily diagrammatic poster wasn’t always easy, it never took long for our audience to discover something they were keen to learn about.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Written by [Aidan Hunter](#)

Feature on Aidan Hunter Ecological Modeller

I'm an ecological modeller working with the [Ecosystems team](#) at [British Antarctic Survey](#) in Cambridge. After a Masters in mathematics I applied for various environmental research roles, including modelling the fluid dynamics of wind turbine arrays, but eventually landed a marine science PhD in fishery statistics and modelling. This involved researching fishery-induced changes to the growth and maturation of commercially important species and developing a novel fish stock assessment model. My work has since focussed on fish food: plankton, particularly in the polar regions. I've developed a range of marine ecology models including an end-to-end ecosystem model, trait-based copepod model, and Lagrangian (particle-tracking) size-structured phytoplankton model. As part of my work with each of these, I devised numerical methods of tuning model parameters to produce statistically optimum fits to multiple data sets – making the models match observed reality. My favourite way of doing this is via Bayesian methods.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

BIOPOLE Outreach

Over the past few months, BIOPOLE has been involved in a number of activities and hatching new plans to promote outreach of our scientific endeavours.

In mid-October 2023, the Sir David Attenborough was alongside in Harwich, UK, undertaking last minute preparations for the BIOPOLE cruise and the journey (fuelled by hydrotreated vegetable oil!) to the Falkland Islands, where the cruise participants will meet her. In the days leading up to her departure she had a flurry of a few hundred visitors as part of her ongoing Communications and Engagement activities (led by [Emily Neville](#) at [BAS](#)). [Nadine Johnston](#) joined the team to talk to members of the public about BIOPOLE and our forthcoming cruise, highlighting the strengths of the Sir David Attenborough in enabling us to conduct multidisciplinary science, particularly in the sea ice zone. As part of a whole-ship-tour, [Nadine Johnston](#) spoke with groups from Scouts and Cubs, a local Harwich high school, the Royal Harwich Yacht Club, Harwich Port staff, and even to BIOPOLE Members who were attending the British Antarctic Family Day tour of the ship! Around this time, [Geraint Tarling](#) and [Nadine Johnston](#) spoke with [Thomas Harding](#) from the National, who was interested in hearing about our programme for potential future features (watch this space!).

As well as plans for celebrating the annual international days of LGBTQIA+ STEM and Polar Pride on the BIOPOLE Southern Ocean cruise (cross reference other article), we will also be celebrating International Antarctica Day on the 1st December to mark this milestone of peace and to inspire future decisions. BIOPOLE Members of the cruise will be participating in the UK Polar Network's annual Antarctic Flags initiative 2023-24, which aims to 'extend the celebrations worldwide, giving new generations the opportunity to learn about the Antarctic Treaty and to share, interpret and cherish the values associated with Antarctica'.

[Nadine Johnston](#) flying a hand drawn flag onboard the RRS Discovery cruise DY158 in the Weddell Sea as part of the UKPN Antarctic Flags Initiative 2022-23

Written by [Nadine Johnston](#) and [Geraint Tarling](#)

BIOPOLE at SOOS Symposium 2023

The [SOOS](#) mission is to facilitate the sustained collection and delivery of essential observations of the Southern Ocean to all stakeholders, through the design, advocacy, and implementation of cost-effective observing and data delivery systems. The SOOS SSC includes several members of the BIOPOLE Community: [Andrew Meijers](#) is a Scientific Member, [Petra ten Hoopen](#) is an Ex-Officio Data Management Sub-Committee co-chair, and [Sian Henley](#) is a co-chair of the Executive Committee.

Several BIOPOLE Community members participated in the first SOOS Symposium 'Southern Ocean in a Changing World', held in Hobart, Australia 14-

21st August. BIOPOLE featured in a range of presentations by [Andrew Meijers](#), [Povl Abrahamsen](#), [Alexander Brearley](#), and [Petra ten Hoopen](#). Together with the lead convenor Alexander Haumann, [Nadine Johnston](#) and [Michael Meredith](#) also delivered a workshop '*Taking the pulse of the Southern Ocean: an internationally coordinated, circumpolar, and year-round mission*', with the goal of soliciting community input to identify the scientific objectives for a 2027-30 fieldwork initiative, '[Antarctica InSynch](#)' and its contribution to the UN Decade of the Ocean for Sustainable Development. This was also attended by other members of the BIOPOLE Community.

[Petra ten Hoopen](#) represented [UK Polar Data Centre](#) (BAS) and was involved in a number of data-related activities in the Inaugural SOOS Symposium 2023. Specifically, Petra chaired the Data System Plenary session with the invited speaker Dr Vito Vitale and two 'How to in SOOSmap' workshops on new functionalities of the Southern Ocean observing systems data portal. She presented on Open Data Reuse, took part in a panel discussion of the workshop 'Creating impact for your observational data beyond research' and organised the Symposium Data Helpdesk as well as a Data Surgery session, where members of the SOOS Data Management Sub-Committee (DMSC) provided one-on-one advice on data issues to the Symposium delegates. Other activities included a visit of colleagues at the Australian Antarctic Division and participation in the Essential Variable Workshop aimed to review Essential Variables relevant for the Southern Ocean. As a Chair of DMSC, Petra organised and chaired the Annual SOOS DMSC meeting that resulted in a number of tangible actions, which were highlighted as valuable to the Southern Ocean community during the SOOS Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) meeting, where she attended and chaired a joint session of the SSC and DMSC team.

Written by [Nadine Johnston](#), [Andrew Meijers](#), [Povl Abrahamsen](#), [Alexander Brearley](#), and [Petra ten Hoopen](#)

BIOPOLE Checks in with the Other NERC LTSM2 Projects

On 16th October, [Geraint Tarling](#), [Adrian Martin](#) and [Yevgeny Aksenov](#) attended a meeting with the six other NERC National Capability projects funded under the LTSM2 scheme.

These projects cover long-term, strategic work across the breadth of the NERC portfolio from agriculture to atmospheric modelling. The idea of the meeting was to identify areas where there was potential for collaboration and the sharing of best practise.

BIOPOLE has common interests with several other LTSM2 projects and these were highlighted and explored further during the meeting. For instance, [CANARI](#) is modelling ocean and atmospheric processes in the North Atlantic and Arctic where there is mutual interest with BIOPOLE in Arctic biogeochemistry and primary production, especially with regards vertical mixing. Further, CANARI will generate storylines of future Arctic change, which will be of great use to our own modelling efforts. [TerraFIRMA](#) is an Earth System Modelling programme, making future climate projections. BIOPOLE will be providing observational data to this programme while benefitting from its Earth system projections out to 2300.

The LTSM2 meeting also highlighted some cross-cutting themes that could lead to future proposal calls. BIOPOLE shared its publication guideline document and promoted its growing ECR group, which will hopefully lead to a linkage of ECRs across the suite of LTSM2 projects.

Written by [Geraint Tarling](#)

Upcoming Relevant Events

International MOSAiC Science Conference 2024

**26 February - 1 March 2024, Alfred Wegener
Institute, Potsdam, Germany**

For more information about the conference,
[please click here](#)

East Meets West Joint BIOPOLE-ACEAS Workshop

14-15 March 2024, Hobart, Tasmania

ICES-PICES 7th International Zooplankton Production Symposium

17-22 March 2024, Hobart, Tasmania

For more information about the symposium and to
register, [please click here](#)

2024 Ocean Decade Conference

10-12 April 2024, Barcelona, Spain

For more information about the conference and to register, [please click here](#)

BIOPOLE Annual Science Meeting

**6-8 March 2024, British Antarctic Survey,
Cambridge**

Save the dates and keep an eye out for the registration, agenda, and further information that will be sent out soon!

